

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility

SPOKE 1– Progress Report _ I Semester

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility
Flagship Project – H2Mobility

Progress Report

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility

SPOKE 1– Deliverable 3.0.2

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.

Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.
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1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of H2Mobility is to contribute to improve the technological readiness to the exploitation of H₂ as the renewable energy vector for the future mobility system. This goal will determine a strong demand for new technologies, new components, and innovative services for green H₂ storage (adsorbing and absorbing materials) and its subsequent distribution and use to provide energy on-demand (fuel cells, internal combustion engines). The activities include the **use of robust and established technology pathways to produce system to store** (e.g. adsorption and absorption in different matrices, chemical storage), **to distribute and to use** (fuel cells, internal combustion engines) **green hydrogen**. This implies innovation activities for the development of new solutions for components and subsystems in order to lower costs, fostering the market acceptance and supporting the creation of local supply chains.

Beside H₂ storage, distribution and use capabilities, the project will also address E-Fuels. In this regard, the research activity will focus mainly on the development of components, technologies and systems for conversion of CO₂ and other vectors into RFNBO (Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin) in order to optimize biocatalytic conversion, with the aim to exploit specific and optimized metabolic pathways. Additionally, the environmental benefits of producing and using RFNBO will be quantified according to LCA based methodology, as per the REDII and ICAO-CORSIA

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per RM in the reporting period

1.2.1 Research Module 1

Research Module n. 1:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen production		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	Envipark	UNITO
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 2.81	Envipark: 1.87 UNITO: 0.22
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis 2) Bio-based processes for H₂ production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H₂ production 		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
1) Objective1/ Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis		

Task 1.1 Technology briefs on Green Hydrogen generation by electrolysis (POLITO DENERG Team; ENVIPARK)

The activity that has been performed in this task is the definition of the research methodology and the structure of the technological briefs on green hydrogen generation by electrolysis. Literature research is ongoing on the state-of-the-art of the electrolysis for low-temperature anion exchange membranes (AEM) electrolyzers and intermediate-temperature proton conducting electrolyzers.

Task 1.2 Technology development – modeling electrolysis system at SRU/stack level (POLITO DENERG Team)

The activity that has been performed in this task is the development of the thermo-electrochemical modeling platform for single cells for the intermediate-temperature proton-conducting technology. The cell model has been developed using CFD software (Comsol) and it is developed up to the boundary with interconnect plates. The model calibration and validation is ongoing using literature data.

Task 1.3 Technology testing – Test procedures/protocols for electrolyzers and components (POLITO DENERG Team; ENVIPARK)

The activity that has been performed in this task is the review of standardized protocols and testing infrastructures for testing Alkaline Membrane electrolyzers. The review of protocols and testing infrastructures for PEM electrolyzers is ongoing.

Task 1.4 Evaluation of r-SOC (reversible Fuel cell) installation in residential and commercial eco-building: permitting procedures, safety aspects for the installation. (ENVIPARK)

The activity addresses a reversible plant system. During the six-month period, the activity was limited to monitoring the evolution of Italian regulations that could potentially be applicable to the type of system in question. This monitoring included, in particular, the "fire prevention technical rule for the identification of methodologies for risk analysis and fire safety measures to be adopted for the design, construction and operation of hydrogen production plants by electrolysis and related storage systems" that is in the process of being approved. This standard is very recently issued and its applicability to the specific case will have to be verified.

2) Objective2/ Bio-based processes for H₂ production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H₂ production

Task 1.5 BIO-Electrochemical processes for H₂ production (POLITO DISAT Team)

During this phase of the project, for what concerned the bio-electrochemical processes for H₂ production, our activities were mainly focused on the selection of commercial materials, commonly used in these devices, combined with the proper arrangement of laboratories needed to accommodate all research activities on these topics.

In particular, for what concerned the material and equipment purchases, we selected all commercial catalysts commonly used in bio electrochemical devices for H₂ production, namely as cathodic catalysts several materials were proposed and investigated in the literature such as platinum, transition metal alloys (nickel-based, Mo₂S₃-based), nitrogen-doped activated carbon; on the contrary, for what concern the anode electrode, commonly it is carbon-based materials, whose surface should improve the bacteria proliferation, since a particular kind of microorganisms were used as catalysts for anodic reactions, able to produce H₂ from water.

Instead, regarding the equipment, we selected H-cells as microbial electrolyzes, leading thus to have the possibility to employ these devices in a single or double chamber mode, investigating the different overall performance.

Task 1.6 Aqueous phase reforming (POLITO DISAT Team)

In this semester, the study has been focused on the valorisation of lignin-rich stream from lignocellulosic ethanol production. The idea is to convert it into biocrude by continuous hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) while hydrogen was produced by aqueous phase reforming (APR) of the HTL aqueous by-product. The effect of Na_2CO_3 and NaOH addition has been investigated both in terms of processability of the feedstock as well as yield and composition of the obtained products. A maximum biocrude yield of 27 wt% was reached in the NaOH -catalyzed runs. A relevant amount of dissolved phenolics were detected in the co-produced aqueous phase (AP), and removed by liquid-liquid extraction using butyl acetate or diethyl ether, preserving the APR catalyst stability and reaching an hydrogen yield up to 146 mmol H_2 L^{-1} AP. Preliminary mass balances integrating HTL and APR showed that the hydrogen provided by APR may account for about 50% of the hydrogen amount theoretically required for upgrading the HTL biocrude, thus significantly improving the process performance and sustainability. Moreover, the LCA methodology has been also used for the first time to assess the environmental impacts of a biorefinery where hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) and aqueous phase reforming (APR) are integrated. Corn stover (residue) and lignin-rich stream (waste) have been evaluated as possible lignocellulosic feedstocks. The global warming potential (GWP) was 56.1 and 58.4 $\text{g}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{MJ}$ biofuel, respectively. Most of the GWP was attributable to the electrolysis step in the lignin-rich stream case and to the thermal duty and platinum use in the corn stover case. Other impact categories were investigated, and an uncertainty analysis was also carried out.

Objective1 and Objective2

Task 1.7 Materials for Hydrogen production (UNITO, POLITO DISAT Team).

POLITO DISAT Team

The catalyst used for the APR reaction is a 5% Pt/C, provided by a commercial supplier in powder form, of which 80% had a size $<106\mu\text{m}$. The catalyst was used as received. Pt/ Al_2O_3 samples prepared by impregnation in DISAT lab has been also tested, for the sake of comparison.

UNITO Team

Green hydrogen production is based on water electrolysis, powered by renewable energies. The use of hydrogen in fuel cells, usually requires high purity hydrogen. So, after production, hydrogen must be purified. Other sources of green hydrogen, e.g. from biomasses, usually produce a gas mixture, from which hydrogen has to be separated.

Several technologies are currently used for hydrogen separation and purification. The current state-of-the-art for hydrogen purification features pressure-swing adsorption (PSA). It targets large-scale production of ultrapure hydrogen, with a recovery of 70-90%, starting from raw mixtures containing 60-90 mol% H_2 . Cryogenic purification of hydrogen is also exploited in large-scale applications, namely petrochemical industry. During the process, raw mixtures are dried and then cooled to separate the impurities by liquefaction. Membrane technology applied to hydrogen purification from natural gas has recently seen a growing development, thanks to lower energy demand and cost compared to PSA and cryogenic methods.

Hydride-forming alloys are suitable for simultaneous purification and storage of contaminated feed streams, being able to supply high-purity hydrogen to fuel cells. The hydrogen-selective storage capability of metal hydrides allows recovery rates ranging from 75% to 90% and assures purity up to 99.9999% from gas streams containing barely 15 vol.% of hydrogen. Absorption and desorption of hydrogen are operated in continuous-flow mode by acting on temperature and pressure. It is necessary to cool down the system during absorption because the hydrogenation reaction is exothermic, whereas hydrogen desorption needs heating.

Output and results:

The overall activities that have been performed in the first reporting period task has been mainly focused on the definition of models, the identification of the research methodology and of technological approaches for hydrogen production via electrolysis and alternative approaches of green H₂ production.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Start experimental activity for H₂ production through different approaches
- Extending analysis to other impacting categories of bio-precursors for H₂ production
- Completing the analysis of existing regulations
- Conclude validation and calibration of models

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n. 2:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen storage		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	UNITO	
Partners involved	POLITO	
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	UNITO: 0.22	POLITO: 0.94
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<p>Innovative solutions will be developed to produce hybrid materials for the chemical storage of hydrogen. This ambitious goal will be achieved by combining species with a high gravimetric hydrogen content such as ammonia borane or with organic aromatic compounds containing heteroatoms such as nitrogen. Within the project, stable materials with up to one hundred release/regeneration cycles with high hydrogen release capacity will be produced. A technical solution will then be implemented that will couple the materials for storage with a controlled release system by means of thermal stimulation based on their confinement in heat exchanger-based systems.</p>		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
Task 2.1 Aminoborane materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT)		
<p>The activities were focused on the creation of solid and sustainable functional “chemical box” for chemically store hydrogen under the form of solid ammonia borane. The strategy deployed was based on the production of layered materials rich derived from nanocrystalline cellulose. This route allowed the formation of layered composited tighten up tougher by hydrogen bond networks. Accordingly, a pressed layer of crystalline nanocellulose was realized coated with a thin layer of palladium deposited by sputtering. Two of these structures were used as external layer with the palladium side in contact with an ammonia borane capsule. The ration between ammonia borane and nanocrystalline cellulose was varied from 20 up to 50 wt.%.</p> <p>The materials produced was tested by using thermal analysis for evaluating hydrogen release and thermodynamic parameters.</p>		
Task 2.2 Aromatic heteroatom compounds materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT)		

During the reporting period, extensive research was conducted on LOHCs (Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers) based on heteroatoms, including N-ethylcarbazole (H0-NEC) and dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (H12-NEC) (16-21). Additional H₂-lean molecules such as 2-benzylpyridine (H0-BPy) (25), (n-methylbenzyl)pyridine (H0-MBP) (26), and indole derivatives were also investigated.

The investigation aimed to select an appropriate candidate for hydrogenation processes, focusing on understanding the hydrogenation pathways and molecular structures of the aforementioned compounds.

The hydrogenation pathways of heteroaromatics were examined, revealing insights into various compounds: H0-NEC hydrogenation led to two major intermediates, H4-NEC and H8-NEC, via chain and direct hydrogenation routes (16-21). H0-NEC hydrogenated faster than H8-NEC.

Benzene structures without methyl groups had low intermediate concentrations, while indole derivatives with different methyl groups followed a similar pathway as 2-methylindole, with varying reaction rates.

This investigation provided valuable insights for selecting an appropriate LOHC candidate, considering hydrogenation pathways and molecular structures.

Task 2.3 Development and integration of storage systems based on metal hydrides in mobility systems (UNITO)

After production and before the use in different applications, hydrogen has to be transported, compressed and stored, so suitable hydrogen handling approaches, based on low-cost, safe, highly efficient and sustainable systems and operating close to ambient temperature and pressure, are needed. In the first Reporting Period, an overview on the state of the art of current technologies for hydrogen storage has been carried out.

In particular, some case studies using metal hydrides as hydrogen carrier have been considered. Hydride-forming intermetallic compounds are divided in three main types, i.e., AB₅, AB₂ and AB, where A and B are alloying elements or combinations thereof. A symbolizes rare-earth elements in AB₅ compounds and d-block metals in AB₂ and AB, while B stands for d-block metals in all three alloy types. Known exceptions are Mg in AB and Al in AB₅. In AB₅, elements different from lanthanum are added to tailor the equilibrium pressure.

Various commercial alloys for hydrogen storage have been selected. The crystal structure has been determined by X-ray diffraction, and the microstructure has been observed by optical and electron microscopy. Powder morphology has been determined by Scanning Electron Microscopy. Thermodynamic and kinetic properties have been determined by a Sievert-type equipment.

A comparison of hydrogen sorption properties in metal powders produced starting from high and low purity materials is planned. The goal is to identify suitable compositions to be used for hydrogen storage in real applications at affordable costs.

Output and results:

Overview on the state of the art of current technologies for hydrogen storage has been carried out
Preliminary analysis and creation of solid functional “chemical box” for H₂ chemical storage in the form of solid ammonia borane.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

A comparison of hydrogen sorption properties in metal powders produced starting from high and low purity materials is planned.

Goal is identification of suitable compositions to be used for hydrogen storage in real applications at affordable costs.

1.2.3 Research Module 3

Research Module n. 3:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen distribution and transport		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	Envipark	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 1.50	Envipark: 1.34
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<p>The task aims to develop methods and procedures to design and validate infrastructures for hydrogen distribution and transport</p>		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
<p>Task 3.1 Techno-economic analysis and system optimization for renewable infrastructure deployment (POLITO DENERG)</p> <p>The activity that has been performed in this task is the application of the optimization model to the optimal design of hybrid renewable energy systems for green hydrogen production.</p>		
<p>Task 3.2 Test procedures/protocols for leak tests on an innovative heat exchanger for HRS application (ENVIPARK).</p> <p>The activity is aimed at defining test protocols useful for the development of high-efficiency heat exchangers for use in hydrogen distribution systems for mobility where high performance is required in terms of heat exchange due to significant pressure variations.</p> <p>This activity saw the start of interlocutions with companies in the supply chain during the semester in order to determine testing needs and specific expertise in leak detection. Based on the evidence gathered, a literature analysis was initiated that was useful for defining the state of the art and planning the design of tests and related test benches in the coming months.</p>		
<p>Task 3.3 Hydrogen distribution via natural gas transport and distribution net (POLITO DISAT)</p> <p>During the specified period, a literature research was conducted on membranes capable of separating hydrogen from hydrogen-methane mixtures. High free volume polymeric membranes, such as PIM, TB polymer, and PI-based membranes, show superior H₂/CH₄ separation performances. However, physical aging and plasticization pose challenges for practical applications of polymeric membranes.</p> <p>MMMs, incorporating porous fillers like MOFs and PAFs, have been explored but generally have unsatisfactory separation performances.</p> <p>CMS membranes, as inorganic membranes, demonstrate excellent H₂ permeability and selectivity. However, addressing brittleness and physical aging is necessary.</p>		
Output and results:		
<p>Identification of models to design optimal hybrid renewable energy systems.</p> <p>Literature research was conducted on membranes capable of separating hydrogen from hydrogen-methane mixtures</p>		
Deviations (if applicable):		

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

To inspire future research, efforts in these areas can advance the development of efficient H₂/CH₄ separation membranes:

- (1) Developing membranes with high permeability and selectivity, considering large-scale production and economic feasibility.
- (2) Controlling or retarding physical aging in polymeric membranes and investigating plasticization resistance.
- (3) Exploring the potential of non-porous nanofillers in MMMs to enhance mechanical strength.
- (4) Improving the flexibility of CMS membranes while addressing separation performance loss due to physical aging.

1.2.4 Research Module 4

Research Module n. 4:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: E-fuels: CO₂ recovery and conversion		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	UNITO	
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 0.35	UNITO: 0.30
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
Research work has been focused on the development of catalysts for hydrogenating CO ₂ to methanol.		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
Task 4.1		
(POLITO DISAT; UNITO)		
<p>Research work has been focused on the development of catalysts for hydrogenating CO₂ to methanol, which is a useful chemical and an alternative liquid fuel. The promoting effect of CeO₂ and ZrO₂ addition on In₂O₃-based catalysts has been investigated, since, according to the literature, In₂O₃-based catalysts are particularly selective in the hydrogenation of CO₂ to methanol, reducing the production of CO even at high space velocities compared to the more common ternary catalysts such as Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ or Cu/ZnO/ZrO₂. The In_xCe_(100-x) and the In_xZr_(100-x) mixed oxides catalysts have been synthesized via gel-oxalate coprecipitation by varying the atomic ratios between the elements, and subsequently, analysed with several characterisation techniques and tested in a fixed bed reactor under different reaction conditions. The addition of different amounts Ce or Zr modifies structure and morphology of the catalysts, promoting the adsorption of CO₂ from 1.8 mmol_{CO₂}·g_{cat}⁻¹ up to 10.6 mmol_{CO₂}·g_{cat}⁻¹. ZrO₂ stabilises the structure and the results suggest that the greater specific activity (168 mg_{CH₃OH}·g_{In₂O₃}⁻¹·h⁻¹ at 300 °C and 2.5 MPa of In₄₀Zr₆₀) could be ascribed to the electronic promotion of Zr. On the contrary, the addition of CeO₂ has not revealed any beneficial effect on the activity. Concerning the stability, In₂O₃-ZrO₂ binary oxides seems to be affected mainly by sintering; whereas In₂O₃-CeO₂ are affected by at least three deactivating phenomena: sintering, chemical reduction of In₂O₃ to metallic indium and coking.</p>		

Consequently, the deactivation rate of these binary oxides increased from $1.04 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ of the In_{100} to $4.13 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ of the $\text{In}_{40}\text{Ce}_{60}$.

Output and results:

Development of catalysts for hydrogenating CO_2 to methanol

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Extending analysis to other high-impact catalysts

1.2.5 Research Module

Explain the work carried out in RM5 during the reporting period by providing details of the activities carried out by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Research Module n. 5:	Start month: M1	End month: M36			
Title: E-fuels: Technologies, components and applications for FC mobility					
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y					
RM Leader	POLITO				
Partners involved	CNR-ITM	ENVIPARK			
Type of action:	Industrial Research				
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 8.28	CNR-ITM: 1.21	Envipark: 1.21		
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):					
Development of new ionic conductive membranes, analysis of innovative technologies for FC manufacturing, design of high efficiency and low incumbrance and mass air compressors for air supply, design of application of FC to road and water mobility, design of novel mechanical bearings for high speed rotors to avoid air compressors in FC-based mobile applications.					
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):					
Summary of the activities envisaged					
Task 5.1 New strategies for ionic conductive membranes					
(CNR-ITM_ Period covered: from [06/04/2023] to [30/04/2023])					
1. Summary					
The main objective of this task is the development of a sustainable protocol for the production membranes based on perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) polymers using non-toxic solvents to replace substances of very high concern (SVHC) traditionally used in the state-of-the-art preparation protocols of ion exchange membranes. Several non-toxic and green solvents were evaluated using the Hansen Solubility Parameters ¹ (HSP) to predict their affinity toward the Nafion (a PFSA membrane widely used in PEMFC). Based on the results, triethyl phosphate (TEP), dihydrolevoglucosenone (Cyrene) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) can potentially be used as green solvents for Nafion membranes preparation, and in general for the substitution of toxic polar aprotic solvents such as dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylacetamide (DMA) and 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP).					

¹ J. Chem. Inf. Model. 2019, 59, 10, 4188–4194

2. Output and results:

Membrane-based operations are generally considered by themselves green and sustainable; however, it is frequently overlooked that the membrane fabrication itself is quite far to be green. Most of the solvents used in industrially relevant membranes productions are hazardous to human health and to the environment and are also currently mentioned as substances of very high concern (SVHC) in different lists guides, such as CHEM 21, GHS and REACH². Therefore, there is great attention today to develop innovative production protocols where harmful solvents are replaced by not toxic substances, to make industrial membrane production more environmental friendly.³

In table 1 the hazard profile of classical solvents used for ion exchange membrane preparation (#1-3), is compared with that of more sustainable alternatives selected in this study (#4-10).

Table 1. Classification of the solvents according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

#	Solvent	Hazard statement(s)	Pictogram
1	N,N-Dimethylacetamide (DMA)	H312 +H332 H319. H360D	
2	N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF)	H226. H312 + H332 H319 H360D	
3	1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP)	H315. H319 H335. H360D	
4	Triethyl phosphate (TEP)	H302 H319	
5	Dihydrolevoglucosenone (Cyrene)	H319	
6	Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	None	None
7	Dimethyl Isosorbide (DMI)	H315 H319 H335	
8	Propylene Carbonate (PC)	H319	
9	Dimethyl carbonate (DMC)	H225	
10	Diethyl carbonate	H226	

H302: Harmful if swallowed; **H312 +H332:** Harmful in contact with skin or if inhaled; **H315:** Causes skin irritation; **H318** Serious eye damage/eye irritation; **H319:** Causes serious eye irritation; **H225:** Highly flammable liquid and vapour; **H226** Flammable liquid and vapour; **H335:** May cause respiratory irritation; **H360D:** May damage the unborn child

² Green Chem. 2016, 18, 288-296

³ Green Chem., 2014, 16, 4034-4059

Serious health hazard

Health Hazard

Flammable

Corrosive

It's worth to note that the first three solvents, classified as SVHC, have serious health hazards and may damage the unborn child. The alternative solvent evaluated (#4-10) are safer and more sustainable. For example dihydrolevoglucosenone (Cyrene) is as a bio-based alternative for dipolar aprotic solvents safe for end-of-life disposal⁴.

Solvents and polymers can be characterised by three parameters: δ_d for dispersion, δ_p for polar and δ_h for hydrogen bonding. The Nafion and the selected solvents were represented as points in a three-dimensional space called HSP space (Figure 1a). Substance with high affinity have similar HSP (or "like dissolves like"). Quantitative evaluation of the solubility of a polymer in a solvent can be represented by the value of R_a [(MPa)^{1/2}], which reflects the distance between the HSPs of both substances:

$$R_a = [4(\delta_{dp}-\delta_{ds})^2 + (\delta_{pp}-\delta_{ps})^2 + (\delta_{hp}-\delta_{hs})^2]^{1/2}$$

where the second subscript refer to polymer (p) or solvent (s)

On the basis of empirical considerations, solvents within $R_a \leq 5 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ are usually good solvents for a given polymer, and those with $R_a > 5 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ are supposed to be non-solvents⁵. Our calculations indicated a good compatibility of the Nafion with TEP, Cyrene and DMSO (Figure 1b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) Distribution and (b) calculated distance polymer/solvent (R_a) in HSPs space

3. Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

In the next reporting period Nafion membranes will be prepared using the three green solvents selected (TEP, Cyrene and DMSO). The protocol will be optimized evaluating the effect of parameters like solvent evaporation conditions and post-treatment of the membranes.

Fundamental will be the electrochemical characterization of the membranes in order to understand the effect of the preparation protocol on membrane performance.

The membranes produced will compared with commercial samples produced with traditional approaches.

Mixed matrix membranes in which an organic and an inorganic phase coexist in synergic way, will be also developed.

5.1.1 Synthesis of microporous polymer based on benzimidazole groups fluorine-free for proton exchange membrane fuel cells (POLITO DISAT)

⁴ Chem. Commun., 2014,50, 9650-9652

⁵ D. W. Van Krevelen, Properties of Polymers, Their correlation with chemical structure, Their numerical estimation and prediction from additive group contributions, Elsevier Amsterdam, 1990

During the recent period, material has been collected to confirm the state of the art in the use of intrinsically microporous polymers in the field of energy applications. In fact, a feature article is currently being produced on this topic, which will be submitted by the end of June. The modifications of PIM (Polymer of Intrinsic Microporosity) that have already been reported in the literature were taken into consideration, and their further modification was carried out to introduce ionizable groups. The first polymer considered for this study is PIM-1, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Synthesis of PIM1

The initial experimental activity focused on the hydrolysis of the cyano groups to carboxylic groups. The reaction was optimized to obtain C-PIM, and various analyses confirmed that, contrary to the literature, the use of high-temperature and high-pressure conditions in a monomodal microwave reactor resulted in nearly perfect hydrolysis, as evidenced by the IR spectrum shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: cPIM (blue)PIM (red) 1729 cm-1 stretching C=O; 3025-3700 cm-1 stretching –OH 2200 cm-1 stretching CN (disappeared)

The next step will involve optimizing the formation reaction of benzimidazoles from carboxylic groups. However, conductivity tests were conducted on a membrane formed from C-PIM, which demonstrated excellent conductivity after overnight conditioning in a 1M KHCO₃ solution, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Explorative conductivity tests

5.1.2 MEA fabrication and electrochemical characterization for fuel cells application (POLITO DISAT)

During the first six months of the project, our research activity related to the Task-MEA fabrication and electrochemical characterization for fuel cells application focused mainly on the development of gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs), defining which commercial catalysts are most efficient for the electrochemical reactions taking place within PEM Fuel Cells and which proton exchange membrane resulted to be the best choice for PEM fuel cells.

Regarding the selection of proton exchange membrane, the choice fell on proton exchange membranes based on Nafion® NR-211, which is one of the unreinforced membranes available on the market and the current technological standard in fuel cells. These membranes are made from chemically stabilized PFSI (perfluoro sulphonic acid) dispersions that are laid on foils and then heat-treated. The commercial product selected for this project is Nafion® NR-211, which is already available in cuttable laminate sheets with a thickness of approximately 25 μm .

Instead for what concerned the selection of catalysts, more interest was expressed in designing an optimized cathode catalyst to improve the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). We selected the ideal catalyst layer towards ORR, namely platinum and we implemented an ultrasonic spray coating technique (USC), involved to optimize the deposition of catalyst layers. Optimization of the process is ongoing.

Task 5.2 Innovative technologies for FC manufacturing and analysis of automation processes in stack packaging and production (ENVIPARK; POLITO DISAT)

5.2.1 Analysis of innovative plasma-based technologies for FC manufacturing (ENVIPARK)

The activity in the semester saw the initiation of state-of-the-art analysis related to the use of plasma technologies in the manufacturing of electrochemical conversion devices employing hydrogen (fuel cells and electrolyzers). The activity involved interaction with a number of international technology providers to have information on the latest developments in terms of processes and enabling technologies.

In particular, the processes examined mainly involved treatments aimed at improving the adhesion of components of different materials (surface cleaning, activation and deposition); in addition, sealing treatments aimed at anti-corrosion coating emerged. The groundwork was thus laid for upcoming activities that will also have an experimental dimension geared toward testing new deposition technologies functional to the elimination of solvent-based primers and adhesives from processes.

5.2.2 Laser-based processing of nanostructured carbon electrodes for FC (POLITO DISAT)

Based on the experimental results obtained and leading to the patent, we are able to produce and design carbon-based materials in the form of nanostructured and bulk materials. The carbonization of the starting polymeric material is induced by CO₂-laser writing and achieved in an ambient atmosphere due to the alkaline treatment to which the starting polymeric material is subjected, as sketched in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7 Process flow followed to obtain a nanostructured-LIG materials by applying CO₂ laser writing in ambient condition.

The nanostructured polymeric material was obtained by implementing electrospinning process, starting from 2 different polymeric solutions:

- 1) PAN-NFs: Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) polymer dissolved in N-N Dimethylformamide. This polymer was selected thank to its high carbonization yield and high amount of nitrogen in its main chain, that can be converted, during the carbonizations induced by CO₂ laser writing, in several nitrogen defects able to improve the catalytic behavior of nanostructured samples towards Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR).
- 2) PVDF-NFs: A polymeric solution based on Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), properly dissolved in a mixture of acetone and N-N Dimethylformamide (1:1). The PVDF was selected because it belongs to the class of fluorinated polymers, widely applied in Fuel Cells devices as membranes capable of guaranteeing final performance comparable to ion exchange membranes based on Nafion, the reference polymer for the realization of such membranes.

As electrospun both of nanofibers, PAN-NFs and PVDF-NFs were treated in an alkaline environment and then processed by CO₂-laser writing under ambient conditions with the main premise of demonstrating the possibility of inducing carbonization of the respective polymeric starting materials, while retaining an adequate level of control over their morphological properties and improving their electrical and electrochemical properties. Great interest will be focused onto the demonstration and investigation that tis nanostructured-LIG materials can be applied not only as conductive backbone of PEM-fuel Cells electrodes, but directly as electrodes already featuring a catalyst layer in the Task 5.2.4.

For what concerned the bulk material, we applied CO₂-laser writing to induce the carbonization in thin continuous membranes, testing the carbonization induced by CO₂-laser writing in Kapton, which resulted to be easily processed with laser, as deeply investigated in the literature.

All obtained results required first of all to optimize the CO₂-laser writing process in order to achieve good electrical behavior of LIG-materials in the direction perpendicular to the material plane. The application of a material as an electrode in fuel cells demands that they have good electrical conductivity in the plane in conjunction with that in the orthogonal direction, which will be denoted hereafter by z. This phase of work has revealed a substantial lack of studies demonstrating the use of LIG electrodes in fuel cells. The reason for this technological limitation is connected with the fact that LIG materials in membrane form are not electrically conductive in the direction perpendicular to the plane. Indeed, the laser writing process induces the transformation of the material from the surface. Thus, during laser writing, a graphene-like layer of material is created from the surface, leaving a residual

layer of insulating polymer at the bottom. Under standard conditions, extending the laser treatment to remove the polymeric region results in embrittlement and irreversible damage to the carbon layer LIG. The research activities involved in this period brought out that:

- 1) The laser process most effectively converts the entire layer of polymeric material into LIG, with no residual insulating layer, if the polymer is nanostructured. This is because the polymers we process by electrospinning arrange themselves into nanofiber membranes that are 'easily' converted into conductive LIG membranes both in the plane and perpendicular direction. The motivation is the limited thickness combined with optimal mechanical behavior due to the nanostructured membranes, which are flexible and stronger, enabling them to withstand 'more aggressive' writing processes. Furthermore, due to the high surface area, the conversion process to carbon takes place at a lower energy input to the material than with continuous membranes.
- 2) Polymers processed in continuous membranes that are not nanostructured (such as Kapton™ with a thickness of 50 μm) always present a residual polymer layer after laser treatment, which cannot be eliminated by changing the duration of exposure to the laser or its power. The presence of this layer has so far limited the experiments of LIG electrodes in fuel cells. Various techniques are presented in the literature that aim to detach the conductive LIG part from the unprocessed polymer and then use it in fuel cells. To date, there is no reported method that avoids these procedures.

In line with the previous considerations, all the results obtained up to this point are the subject of a new patent to overcome these highlighted technological limitations.

5.2.3 Electrohydrodynamic methods for catalysts deposition (POLITO DISAT)

During the first six months of the task 5.2.3, the main goal was the optimization of electrospray process to enrich a uniform distribution of catalyst layer onto carbon-based electrode. Electrospray process is an electrohydrodynamic process that ensure the deposition of dried nanodrops, directly onto a specific substrate, without the necessity of a binder to connect them with the substrate. The formation of nanodrops was directly tuned by applied voltage, that induced a charge distribution inside polymeric solution, that interact one with each other, insuring thus repulsive forces. When repulsive forces overcome the surface tension and if the rheological viscosity is too low to avoid the formation of a continuous charged polymeric jet, the nanodrops' formation was ensured. With the main purpose to compare two different nanostructures, the first one obtained by implementing ultrasonic spray coating, as deeply described in the Task 5.1.2, and the second one designed by applying electrospray process, we used the same polymeric solution contained catalyst powders (10wt% of Pt onto carbon, purchased from Sigma Aldrich), ionomer solution (5wt% of Nafion in water) and solvents isopropanol and deionized water (IPA: DI) with a volume ration of 3:4. Differently from ultrasonic spray coating process, one of the main limitations for electrospray process, which must be overcome, is the optimization of composition of initial solution, required to achieve a uniform distribution of nanodrops and, at the same time, the correct evaporation of solvent to ensure the collection of dried nanodrops onto the substrate's surfaces. The first reached results confirmed non-uniform deposition of the starting solution and complicated solvent removal during the flight phase of the electrospray process. The presence of a low concentration of polymer, dissolved within the starting solution, is probably required to ensure the formation of nanodrops and at the same time the correct removal of the solvent, which particularly affects the uniform distribution of the final catalyst

5.2.4 Microwave Synthesis of Pt-free catalysts for PEMFCs (POLITO DISAT)

Starting from obtained results in the Task 5.2.2 and with the main aim to develop LIG-nanostructured electrodes, featuring also as catalyst layers, in this Task, the study of these electrodes was initiated in parallel. Indeed, since one of the main objectives is to apply these LIG-nanostructured electrodes as an innovative and low-cost catalyst capable of replacing platinum, which is currently used as the ideal catalyst for the cathodic oxygen reduction reaction in fuel cells, it is necessary to implement electrochemical characterizations to establish the electrochemical properties of LIG-nanostructured electrodes. It has been deeply demonstrated in the literature that a catalyst must be able to supply as many electrons as possible close to the theoretical value of 4, thus guaranteeing the direct oxygen reaction (ORR), while limiting the intermediate reduction reaction, the one requiring only 2 electrons and leading to the production of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), which leads to damage of the catalytic material and electrode. Noble metals, with a focus on platinum (Pt), are considered ideal catalysts for ORR,

presenting certain limitations, such as high cost, low quantity available in nature and low chemical resistance. In order to investigate the electro-catalytic properties of the proposed carbonaceous materials obtained by CO₂ laser writing, the RRDE technique and cyclic voltammetry (CV) were implemented and the electro-catalytic activity of the carbonaceous material was compared with that of Pt, used as a reference catalyst.

The RRDE technique defines the catalytic 'pathways' of LIG-nanostructured electrodes, compared with those provided by Pt, by performing a four-electrode characterization. In order to carry out all these characterizations, the LIG-nanostructured electrodes were deposited onto 'working electrode', consisting of a disc of 'glassy carbon' and a platinum ring (known as the Pt ring) and compared with the Pt/C catalyst layer used as the reference material. The counter electrode is a Pt wire, while the reference electrode is silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl).

The electrolyte was a water-based solution contained 0.1M KOH (pH=7). During RRDE measurements, the disc potential was varied in the voltage range of -0.3 V to -0.8 V (at a rotation speed of 2500 RPM and a scan rate of 5mV s⁻¹), while a potential of 0.2 V was used for the Pt electrode. During the RRDE measurement, the disc current (I_D) and the platinum ring current (I_R) are directly measured, and as a function of these values, the number of electrons transferred (n) and the percentage of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O⁻%) produced can be indirectly determined, using Equation 2:

$$H_2O^{-}\% = 200 \times \frac{I_R/N}{I_D + I_R/N} \quad n = 4 \times \frac{I_D}{I_D + I_R/N} \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, N represents the efficiency of current collection by the Pt ring. The disc current (I_D) represents the reduction pathway that requires 4 electrons for the oxygen reduction reaction to occur, while the Pt ring current (I_R) refers to the production of hydrogen peroxide. Therefore, the higher the I_D, the better the electro-catalytic activity of the material under study, which is therefore able to provide as close to 4 electrons as possible. During this phase of the project, the RRDE technique and CV were applied to evaluate the electro-catalytic properties of the LIG-nanostructured electrodes, obtained from PVDF nanofibers and PAN nanofibers. **Figure 8** shows the trends of the disc and Pt ring currents, highlighting that the disc current, both when the carbonized PAN-NFs and PVDF-NFs were analyzed, is higher than the Pt ring current. All these electrochemical results allowed confirming the good electro-catalytic properties of the two nanostructured materials for the oxygen reduction reaction. Furthermore, by analyzing the trends of the respective currents, it can also be observed that the trends obtained for PAN-NFs and PVDF-NFs are comparable with respect to the reference catalytic material, Pt.

Figure 8 a) Disc current and b) Ring current obtained from RRDE measurements conducted on the following samples: PAN-NFs and PVDF-NFs and Pt/C reference. c) Electron number and percentage of hydrogen peroxide calculated by RRDE characterization for the same samples

In line with these results, it can also be shown that a number of electrons tending towards 4 is guaranteed for both nanostructured samples, guaranteeing a low ring current measurement as a direct consequence. By analyzing the catalytic properties of the two materials PVDF-NFs and PAN-NFs carbonized by writing with a CO₂ laser, and comparing them with those of Pt, it can be seen that PVDF-NFs provide an electron number of 3.95, PAN-NFs provide an electron number of 3.83, both tending towards the ideal and theoretical value of 4.

Task 5.3 Test procedures/protocols for FC and components (ENVIPARK; POLITO-DISAT)

All the designed Gas Diffusion Electrode, prepared and designed in the previous Task (Task 5.1.2, 5.2.2 and 5.2.4) must be assembled and their electrical and electrochemical properties must be investigated. During this phase of the projects, two different techniques were implemented to define the electro-catalytic properties of GDE

electrodes, developed and designed in parallel with the following Task. With the main purpose to investigate GDEs' electrochemical properties towards direct-Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR), the first series of experiments and tests focused on the use of the Rotating Ring Disk Electrode (RRDE) and involved the direct bonding of GDE electrodes to glassy carbon by Nafion solution (5wt% of Nafion dissolved in water and aliphatic solution). As described in the Task 5.2.4, RRDE technique and Cyclic Voltammetry were performed using a CH instruments (760D electrochemical station and an ALS RRDE-3A instrument). In order to design an innovative and cheaper catalyst layer towards ORR that could be commonly employed in Fuel Cells, these measurements should be conducted using two different electrolytes, leading thus to compare different electrocatalytic activities.

The first electrolyte is a water-based solution containing 0.1M KOH, saturated in oxygen; while, on the contrary, the second electrolyte is composed of 0.1M of perchloric acid (HClO_4), able to mimic the same acid conditions that can be reached in a PEM-Fuel Cell. The first achieved results were obtained by providing RRDE measurements in KOH water-based electrolyte, leading thus to confirm the suitability of nanostructured LIG-NFs as Pt-free catalyst layers for ORR, as described in the Task 5.2.4

The other important procedure, implemented to test the electrocatalytic activity of GDEs' electrodes, was identified by GDE setup characterizations, which has recently received increasing attention as a simple tool for testing the catalytic activity of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in the proximity of catalytic sites with the aim of reproducing the conditions characteristic of a proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC). The GDE configuration, involved in the laboratory, was composed by a Teflon cell (Gaskatel Flex-Cell). The catalytic layer is direct in contact with a water-based electrolyte, containing 2M of perchloric acid, which allowed mimicking the high-stress conditions that can develop during operation of the complete PEM Fuel Cell, ensuring, however, a good controllability of all operating parameters. Gas Diffusion Layer was in contact with the part of cells inside which Oxygen is supplied. At this phase of project, first results reached when this configuration was implemented, were properly described in the Task 5.1.2 and concern the electrocatalytic properties of GDE electrodes, obtained by platinum deposition, through ultrasonic spray coating, on commercial carbon paper.

Task 5.4 Fuel cells stack modeling and BoP design (POLITO-DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The activity that has been performed in this task is the development of a dynamic model at system level (Matlab-Simulink) of a small-size PEMFC stack for the design of control strategies to be implemented at vehicle level.

Task 5.5 FC powered small hydrogen electric propelled boat (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The first part of the work has involved a research on the state of the art of hydrogen-powered boats to identify the current application of hydrogen in the field of interest of the task, the actual challenges, the aspects that are still to be developed and the opportunities for innovation. Moreover, a market analysis on fuel cells systems was carried out to understand their impact in terms of weight/volume for a given power demand. Finally, the work has involved some considerations on the possibility to mount an hydrofoil to limit the power demand, that would affect the size of the fuel cell, and so facilitate the application to a small boat.

Hydrogen-powered boats: an overview

The first hydrogen-fueled vessel ready for commercialization was unveiled in Austria in 2009 as part of the Future Project Hydrogen. It was a small boat, powered by a 4 kW proton exchange membrane fuel cell, a photovoltaic system for the generation of green hydrogen through water electrolysis and a 0.7 kg hydrogen storage tank at 350 bar pressure. This boat had zero greenhouse gas emissions and offered double the range and shorter refueling times than conventional battery-powered boats of the same size operating in Lake Traunsee [1]. Although the boat did not achieve market success, likely due to the high cost and the lack of infrastructure for hydrogen supply and distribution, it was the first instance of a commercialized hydrogen boat with a regenerative system [2].

Despite the setback, the idea of using hydrogen as an alternative fuel continued to attract significant interest. The benefit over internal combustion engines was clear in terms of eliminating CO₂ emissions. Compared to battery-only electric vehicles, the trade-off was related to specific energy. According to [3], if one considers the weight of fuel cells, H₂ storage tanks, auxiliary components (dehumidification system, ventilation and control electronics) and batteries for energy storage or for power management in transient conditions, the useful energy per mass of a hydrogen propulsion system at 350 bar pressure can have at least twice the specific energy of batteries alone.

Nowadays, fuel cells are an attractive option for maritime transport due to their negligible emissions of pollutants such as SO_x and NO_x into the atmosphere, as well as their reduced system noise compared to conventional internal combustion propulsion systems [4]. Various types of vessels using fuel cells as an energy generation system have been developed since the 2000s. The fuel sources can vary from diesel, LNG, methanol to hydrogen. Fuel cells can also be hybridized with batteries depending on the application.

A recent review summarizes the developments up to 2023 [5]. One commercialized project is the Nemo H₂ boat, which operates as a public transport service in Amsterdam. This vessel can carry 88 passengers and reach a maximum speed of 8.6 knots. The propulsion system consists of a combination of hydrogen-fueled fuel cells and batteries, with a total power of 60 kW [6]. The Hydrogenesis vessel, which provides local river transport in Bristol, has a capacity of about 10 passengers, a maximum speed of 7 knots, a total power of 12 kW and a hybrid hydrogen fuel cell and battery propulsion system [7]. There are also notable applications of hydrogen fuel cell systems for medium and large-sized boats: the FLAGSHIPS project funded by the European Union, which involves 11 partners from the naval industry, has led to the development of river boats for people, vehicles and goods with power ranging from 600 kW to 1200 kW. This is the project with the highest power capacity that uses hydrogen-fueled fuel cells [8].

In general, it can be noted that the current projects mainly focus on the development of boats and ferries for passenger transport, using hydrogen-fueled fuel cells as the propulsion system, with a prevalence of 63%. Only 34% of the projects under development consider hydrocarbons as fuel [5].

The analysis of the state of the art reveals that significant progress has been made to overcome some of the challenges associated with the application of hydrogen fuel cells in the marine sector. The demonstration projects conducted have verified the technical feasibility of fuel cell power systems in terms of power capability, safety, reliability and durability. Moreover, important improvements have been achieved in energy efficiency and reduced emission of pollutants during the operation of marine fuel cells. However, some remaining challenges need to be addressed, such as the still limited power capacity for long-distance transport, the need for more data on durability and reliability in real-world usage scenarios, and high initial and operational costs. It must also be taken into account that the fueling infrastructure is a key factor for the commercial application of fuel cell systems, especially when the fuel used is hydrogen.

The efforts in the development of hydrogen-based technology are justified by the experimental evidence, and with further investments and research, these technologies are expected to address the remaining issues and become a promising solution for sustainable marine transport in the near future [4]. Furthermore, it can be observed that the current projects focus on medium or large-sized boats, while there is a lack of projects that aim to develop small-sized boats, which could be interesting for navigation in inland waters and in environmentally and naturally protected areas.

Market analysis

The introduction of hydrogen propulsion opens up a wide range of challenges. First, there is the right balance between storage, consumption and power requirements. Then there are many considerations about the need for a battery. For example, to meet peak energy demands or for safety reasons. Then all these aspects have to be integrated into the system volumes and weights.

As with all technical applications, market research has been carried out and it defines a very heterogeneous scenario. It is the result of a wide range of applications. From industrial power generation to automotive. The market research has focused on both storage aspects and weight/volume requirements for a given power demand. Figure is linked to the storage characteristics of many available tanks. The trends reported highlight two main aspects. The first is that the volume of the tank required to store more hydrogen does not increase linearly with the amount of hydrogen stored. This is a good thing because, for applications with high H₂ consumption, the volume of tanks does not grow too fast. The second aspect is that the working pressure/weight parameter decreases as the H₂ storage capacity increases. This aspect is related to the reaching of a maximum allowable storage pressure for tanks, which, on the other hand, continues to increase their weight.

Figure 9. Storage volume and weight

Figure 9 and Figure 10 describe some interesting aspects. Figure 9 relates the power generated by a set of fuel cells (set produced by the manufacturer and ready for use) to both weight and total volume. Obviously, the higher the power, the higher the weight and volume, but the interesting aspect is that both trends follow a quadratic scheme and also overlap.

Figure 10. Fuel cell weight and volume on power demand

Figure 10 shows the relationship between volume and power. There's no trend to be found in all this data, but if we restrict the data set to just one manufacturer (the circled area), we see that in order to increase the performance of their products, they keep the current the same and increase the voltage output by adding more cells. This action is obviously related to volume growth.

Figure 1. Fuel cell current and voltage on volume

A case study: small hydrofoil boat

One possibility is to consider a small hydrogen-foiling boat, which overall shape will be similar to the one reported in Figure 112. The possible features of such a boat are reported in Table 2.

Figure 112. Example of the considered boat type

Table 2. Boat main dimensions

Weight	500 kg
Length	~ 5.5 m
Width	~ 2 m
Draft	~ 1.2 m

Through the analyses done to date, it has been feasible to identify the key qualities that should be connected to a hydrofoil's shape to deliver the most appropriate performance for the application. The efficiency (lift over hydrodynamic resistance) polar is depicted as a function of speed on a graph in Figure 12. The power consumption produced by the foil alone under the given conditions is also indicated overlaid on these patterns. These findings, which were acquired by panel method evaluations, outline the circumstances (starting with takeoff) under which the hydrofoils can sustain the hull (500 kg). The speed and angle of attack were the sole modifications involved to satisfy this requirement. The diagrammed trends are related to five distinct configurations to emphasise the impact of airfoil and shape selection.

Figure 12. Efficiency and power demand trends

Figure 13 displays the hydrodynamic profiles taken into consideration. The configurations under consideration are built on various pairings of the three profiles. Table contains the profiles' specifics.

Figure 13. Airfoils shape

Table 3. Hydrofoil's airfoils

	Root airfoil	Tip airfoil
Hyd. Eppler	Eppler 393	Eppler 393
Hyd. NACA	Naca 632615	Naca 632615
HYD, Mixed	Eppler	Ag 04

The configurations depicted in the blue, green, and orange curves have the same exterior geometry (AR, TR, \bar{C} and S), but have distinct hydrodynamic profiles (hydrofoil sections). It is clear from this that the efficiency maximum's location changes substantially, and the power curve's shift at high speeds is more pronounced while it is practically superimposable at low speeds.

On the other hand, the yellow and violet curves have the same hydrodynamic profile as the green curve (chosen because it delivers the highest performance) but differ in shape. The speed of the peak locations and the lowest take-off speed both significantly change as a result of the variation of the geometric properties.

All of these factors add up to the conclusion that calibrating the geometry of the foil will be necessary to achieve the best performance at the right speeds, depending on the design context. Take a lagoon setting, for instance, where navigation cannot occur at high speeds. In this case, we will favour configurations that are most similar to the outcomes of the yellow curve. On the other side, one will tend towards outcomes nearer to the purple curve as performance (measured as maximum cruising speed) is raised.

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Task 5.6 Analysis of the state of the art of dynamic gas journal bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The activities carried out in this task by DIMEAS Department are aimed at analysing the state-of-the-art of the dynamic gas journal bearings, which can support turbo-compressors of small size introducing low friction without the need of an external compressed air supply. In particular the Herringbone Grooved gas Journal Bearings (HGJB) and thrust bearings (HGTB) are considered in this task.

The second goal is to investigate the analytical and numerical methodologies for modeling such bearings. This activity is preliminary to the development of models useful to simulate such bearings.

The Herringbone Grooved gas bearings

Such bearings were firstly developed in 50s and 60s: in [1] the so-called Narrow Groove Theory (NGT) was firstly developed to investigate the thrust bearings with herringbone pattern. This theory was then further developed in [2] for journal bearings.

The thrust bearing sketched in figure 14 presents some grooves of proper depth machined on the rotor surface; their purpose is to create an air pumping action due to rotation. The pressure distribution that occurs in the bearing as a result of the air input flow creates the axial load carrying capacity. Different groove configurations are possible, with air lubricant pumped inwards, outwards or both [3].

The herringbone-grooved journal bearing is sketched in figure 15, where the inclined grooves machined on the shaft surface are visible. Such grooves, of proper geometry and inclination respect to the axial direction, are responsible of the air pumping action inside the bearing. As a result of this action, a pressure distribution occurs between the journal and the rotating shaft, thus making possible a radial load carrying capacity of the bearing.

Figure 15: sketch of a herringbone-grooved gas journal bearing, from ref [2]

The NGT is a simplified theory as it assumes an infinite number of grooves and local incompressibility of the lubricant along the circumferential direction. According to this theory, the pressure profile along the circumferential direction is smooth and does not consider discontinuities of the groove-ridge pairs, thus simplifying the modeling. In case the discontinuity is considered, a sawtooth pressure profile is obtained. This can be done with more recent FEM approaches [4] and full transient analysis [5]. Anyway, the NGT is suitable for a first design of the bearings as it allows a quite accurate estimation of the axial and radial load carrying capacities. As demonstrated in [6-7], the NGT is in a quite good accordance with the experimental results.

The NGT is also able to evaluate the stability of shaft with HGJB [8-9]. A problem that may occur at high speeds is a self-excited instability responsible of a sudden crash of the shaft with the bearings. Of course, this event must be avoided by designing accurately the rotor-bearings system in terms of the shaft mass, inertia and bearings geometry.

The unbalance response analysis is a crucial aspect that must be considered when verifying experimentally the numerical models: in [10-11] unbalance measurements were carried out for a validation of the linearized coefficients of the gas films in journal bearings. Therefore, it is essential an experimental validation of the numerical models to be able to accurately predict the stiffness and damping properties of HGJBs.

The applications of Herringbone Grooved gas bearings

Gas bearings are used since 60s in various applications such as turbocompressor, turbochargers/expanders [12], gas turbines [13], air cycle machines [14], MEMS [15,16]. More recently they find good challenge in fuel cell [17]

and heat pump applications [18]. The power of the turbomachinery supported by gas bearings ranges from some Watts to 150 kW, while the rotational speeds range from 10 to 500 krpm.

Among all types of gas bearings (externally pressurized or dynamic, with rigid or compliant surfaces), the grooved bearings have very interesting features (compactness and simple manufacturing) which make them very suitable for the oil free and small-scale turbomachinery sector. Automotive turbochargers [19] and turbocompressor for refrigeration [20] are two examples of successful application of such bearings.

The methodologies of investigation

Different methodologies of investigations are possible in order to overcome the difficulties introduced by the groove/ridge discontinuity in the air gap. A first approach is the NGT previously mentioned, which considers an infinite number of grooves and provides a simplification of the problem [21]. In this case, an infinite number of infinitesimal groove ridge pairs are considered to obtain a smooth pressure profile along the circumferential direction. An alternative approach is to model the groove/ridge discontinuity with finite elements [22] or finite volume approaches [23]. The NGT was then reformulated in [24] with a two-scale approach, aimed at refining the macroscale NGT model considering the local compressibility effects at the microlevel across the groove-ridge pair.

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Task 5.7 Development of a numerical model of bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The so-called Narrow Groove Theory (NGT) has been individuated to be an effective instrument for a first estimation of the load carrying capacity of gas thrust bearings with herringbone pattern [1]. An extension of this theory has been developed in [2] for the estimation of the radial load capacity of journal bearings. Here below are described the assumptions on the base of this theory for the thrust bearings.

Task 5.7.1: NGT for estimating the load capacity of a gas thrust bearing with herringbone pattern

Geometrical parameters of the thrust bearing:

a1: groove width along the circumferential direction

a2: ridge width along the circumferential direction

b=r3-r2: radial length of the groove

c=r2-r1: radial length of the smooth surface bearing

r1: internal radius

r2: intermediate radius

r3: external radius

h1: air gap in correspondence of the groove

h2: air gap in correspondence of the ridge

θ : angle of inclination of the grooves with respect to the radial direction

The thrust bearing is composed by a smooth disk rotating on a grooved fixed surface. The bearing has an internal part with smooth surface, in which the air gap is constant ($h=h_2$) and an external part with grooves machined on its surface, in which the air gap is $h=h_1$. Here below is a frontal representation of the thrust bearing (left) and a sketch of the bearing in a rectangular domain, in which the x axis coincides with the circumferential direction and the y axis with the opposite of the radial direction. In this case, the curvature of the bearing is neglected.

The thin film flow equations are considered in order to develop an analytical model able to estimate the load capacity of the thrust bearing. The continuity equation is valid inside the domain, which brings to considering the Reynolds equation. We make the following assumptions:

- compressible lubricant
- pressure independent on x (circumferential direction)

Boundary conditions:

- $p=p_0$ at $r=r_3$ and $r=r_1$
- $p=p_1$ at $r=r_2$

Load capacity of the internal zone

The internal zone is in limits $b < y < b+c$ or $r_1 < r < r_2$. In this zone the air gap is constant and equal to $h=h_2$. The load capacity per unit of circumferential length is given by

$$F = \int_b^{b+c} p - p_0 dy = \frac{2P^3 - p_0^3}{3P^2 - p_0^2} c - p_0 c$$

where P is the average pressure at $y=b$ ($r=r_2$). The flux in the radial direction is defined as

$$V = \int_0^h \rho v dz = \rho \left[-\frac{h^3}{12\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \right]$$

so the mean pressure P can be expressed as a function of the flux:

$$P^2 = p_0^2 + \frac{24\mu RT}{h^3} Vc$$

Load capacity of the external zone

The external zone is in limits $0 < y < b$ or $r_2 < r < r_3$. In this zone the air gap is equal to $h = h_2$ in the ridges and $h = h_1$ in the grooves. The hypotheses done for this region are:

- pressure p is continuous at the edge of the groove
- the flux across the edges of the grooves are continuous
- pressure is periodic in x with period $a_1 + a_2$
- the mean flux in the y direction is independent on y and equal to V

According to these assumptions it is possible to obtain the pressure distribution.

The model is going to be set up according to the equations. The further steps will be described in the next deliverables.

[1] R.T.P. Whipple, Theory of the Spiral Grooved Thrust Bearing with Liquid or Gas Lubricant, Technical Report, Great Britain Atomic Energy Research Establishment, Harwell, Berks, England, 1951.

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Task 5.8 Realization of a demonstrator (POLITO-DIMEAS)

During the first semester this task has not yet been activated independently: results from Task 5.6 and Task 5.7 will be used as starting input for the next future.

Output and results:

Development of innovative production protocols where harmful solvents are replaced by not toxic substances, to make industrial membrane production more environmentally friendly.

State of the art analysis in the use of PIM (Polymer of Intrinsic Microporosity) in the field of energy applications.

Initial experimental activity focused on the hydrolysis of the cyano groups to carboxylic groups

Selection of commercially available catalysts and proton exchange membrane for PEM fuel cells.

state-of-the-art analysis related to the use of plasma technologies.

CO₂-laser writing process was optimized in order to achieve good electrical behavior of LIG-materials in the direction perpendicular to the material plane.

Optimization of electrospray process to enrich a uniform distribution of catalyst layer onto carbon-based electrode.

Development of a dynamic model at system level (Matlab-Simulink) of a small-size PEMFC stack.

State of the art of hydrogen-powered boats to identify the current application of hydrogen in the field of interest of the task.

State-of-the-art of the dynamic gas journal bearings, which can support turbo-compressors of small size introducing low friction.

Goal is to investigate the analytical and numerical methodologies for modeling such bearings

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

In the next reporting period Nafion membranes will be prepared using the green solvents, evaluating the effect of parameters like solvent evaporation conditions and post-treatment of the membranes.

The next step will involve optimizing the formation reaction of benzimidazoles from carboxylic groups.

Development of GDE for PEM fuel cells.

Upcoming experimental activities will focus on testing new deposition technologies functional to the elimination of solvent-based primers and adhesives from processes.

Applying LIG-nanostructured electrodes as an innovative and low-cost catalyst capable of replacing platinum.

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects:

Action	Key Indicator	Flagship overall target	Flagship progress
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	2	
	Number of publications	20 journal papers /publications in international conferences	
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	2	
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	16	21
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	146,5 PM	20,25 PM

2. IMPACT

This first phase of the project has been mainly devoted to:

- the implementation of the management structure of the FP and the coordination of the different actors involved
- the final identification and set up of the research activities

For this reasons, the number of outcomes and products is still limited.

No publication is available yet, however a Journal publication and three conference contributions have been submitted and are currently under review.

No IPR has been produced yet. Three datasets are currently being compiled and will be finalized by the next reporting period.

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc.)

In this initial phase of the applied research activities the engagement of industry has been mostly linked to the involvement of the Stakeholders Committee. Moreover, the contents of the Flagship have been presented in different meetings with companies during the events for the launch of cascade calls. Meetings have been also organised by scientific coordinators with companies interested in the topics of the flagship. All the researchers involved in the FP are intensifying their research relationships with companies. To this end, they are establishing relationships with new companies and to identify topics of real interest where researchers' expertise may be of interest.

4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

The activities of this first phase of the project were mostly devoted to the set-up of the research activities, the recruitment of personnel and the revision of the state of the art, that will allow advanced research activities in the next steps of the project.

ANNEXES

LIST OF DELIVERABLES

Add actual delivery dates (or new due date for late deliverables, together with an explanation for the delay). In the Comments, please indicate if the deliverable was achieved as planned or not.

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R – Restricted; C – Confidential; S – Secret.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM Number]	[short name]	[R – Document, report] [DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA – data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP – Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU – Public] [SEN – Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[Pending] [Draft] [Submitted] [Rejected] [Approved] [Removed]	[insert comments]
D1	H2Mobility Report 1	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	12				
D2	H2Mobility Report 2	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	24				
D3	H2Mobility Report 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	DEM	PU	30				
D4	H2Mobility Report 4	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	36				

Table 1: Deliverables

LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM number]	[beneficiary short name]	[means of verification as in Annex 1]	[Month]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment]
MS1	Milestone 1	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D1	M12				
MS2	Milestone 2	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D2	M24				
MS3	Milestone 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D3	M30				
MS4	Milestone 4	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D4	M36				

Table 2: Milestones

LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

State of play: Give the state of play of the risks that were identified (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
[risk number]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment (mandatory if no risk mitigation measures were applied or planned risk mitigation measures were not applied)]

Table 3: Risks

PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT

Provide details about the project results. Please focus on the content of the results, for example discoveries and theories, products, services, methods etc. Publications, intellectual property rights, datasets, software, algorithms, protocols etc. will be linked to these results later in separate tables. It will also be possible to add these to the project as a whole.

Examples:

- The project developed a new medical device, which is described in two publications and later patented. Instructions: List the medical device here (as 'PROD: Product') and add publications to this product in dedicated sections. When you have information about the patent application, add it in a dedicated section.
- The project developed a new scientific theory which is described in several publications. Instructions: List the name and potential of the theory here (as 'SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory') and add relevant publications later in dedicated sections.
- The project develops a high potential industrial process and is currently at the stage of prototyping. Instructions: List the industrial process here (as 'PROC: Industrial process') and indicate the prototyping stage under 'Steps undertaken towards exploitation'. If there is a registered prototype, add the registered prototype in a dedicated section.

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
[name]	[SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory...] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)] [PO — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy] [EVNT — Event (conference, seminar, workshop)] [STAFF — (qualified personnel exchanges)] [LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula)] [INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities]	[TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstration or testing] [Intellectual property management] [Complying with regulatory framework] [Contribution to standards] [Feasibility Study] [Market Study] [Business plan] [Other]	[Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created] [Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market] [Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply] [Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products]

Table 5: Publications

DATASETS

Short Name:	
Description of datasets:	
Data origin:	
Data type:	
Data Formats:	
Useful for whom:	
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	<p>[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]</p>
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	<p>Persistent identifier and project metadata (provision of metadata and documentation) - URL to repository</p>
Accessibility:	<p>[Fully open à repository] [Partially open à repository and access methods] [no à motivation]</p>

Interoperability:	<i>Standards for interoperability</i>
Reusability:	<i>Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation [CCBY or equivalent] [CCO or equivalent to CCO] [Other]</i>
Open	<i>[YES][Partially][NO] - Access methods</i>

Table 6: Data sets

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
[Patent] [Trademark] [Registered design] [Utility model] [Other]	[insert title of the application]	[OPTION for international applications of patents [insert IP international organisation code] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for national applications of patents [insert country code (two letters)] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for other registered IPR: [insert application reference country code (two letters) or organisation code]] [insert alpha numeric identifier]] [insert EPO/google patent format] [insert application ID]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert owner name(s)]	[YES] [NO] [N/A]	[insert reference]

Table 7: IPRs

OTHER RESULTS

Type of result	Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	TRLs	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for the result service/webpage hosting the result (if available)	What license is the result under
[Software] [Workflow] [Protocol] [Prototype] [Other]	[insert description]	[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [Other]	[insert PID reference]	[insert URL]	[CCBY or equivalent] [CC0 or equivalent to CC0] [Other]

Table 8: Other results

IMPACT in terms of TRLS, SDGs, KSOs

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: [an item.]	Expected by Project 'end:
RM1 _ TRL 4	[TRL1- Basic principles observed]
RM2 _ TRL 4	[TRL2- Technology concept validated]
RM3 _ TRL 4	[TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept]
RM4 _ TRL 4	[TRL4 - Technology validated in lab]
RM5 _ TRL 4	[TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment]
Current status: [an item.]	[TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment]
No change	[TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment]
	[TRL8- System complete and qualified]
	[TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment]
	[Not applicable]

Table 9: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life Below Water	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life on Land	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
No Poverty	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant]
	[Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Good Health and Well-being	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Reduced Inequality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]

Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Responsible Consumption and Production	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Quality Education	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
International cooperation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Please explain your choice:	[insert text]

Table 10: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations	A competitive and secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cyber-secured digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	
KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	
KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
	Affordable and clean energy	
	Smart and sustainable transport	
	Circular and clean economy	

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<p>KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health</p>	<p>A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats</p>	
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Table 11: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE